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Nationwide quality of outpatient palliative care assessed by different palliative care providers in Switzerland

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Quality of outpatient palliative care assessed by direct service providers, regional palliative care organisations and healthcare authorities – A nationwide survey from Switzerland

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Abstract

Purpose: A prior study used 13 indicators to assess overall palliative care quality: Switzerland scored 88 points (top quartile: 82–93). This study assessed the quality of outpatient palliative care in Switzerland, and identified criteria associated with higher quality.

Method: Cross-sectional study surveying direct service providers, 14 palliative care organisations, 26 healthcare authorities. The 13 indicators assessed outpatient palliative care quality. Multivariable regression analysed associations between established criteria and higher scores.

Results: The survey was completed by 141 participants (≥ 4 per canton) including 96 (68%) direct service providers, all palliative care organisations and cantonal authorities. Nurses accounted for 52% ($n = 73$, including 61 providers). Participants agreed with 'treated kindly' (98% agreed), 'controlled pain and discomfort' (98%), 'appropriate levels of life extending treatments' (95%) but disagreed with 'costs are no barrier' (44% disagreed), 'good coordination' (19%), 'cared for/die at place of choice' (14%). All 13 indicator questions were answered by 100 participants (71%), resulting in a median score of 82. Of participants seeing patients, 85% (82/97) answered all 13 questions, only 41% (18/44) of those without patient contact ($p < 0.001$). 'Recording desired place of death' (odds ratio [OR] 6.7, 95% confidence interval [95%CI] 2.7–21.3), 'preventing critical incidents' (OR 5.8, 95%CI 2.8–13.0), 'recording critical incidents' (OR 2.1, 95%CI 1.3–3.7) were independently associated with higher scores.

Conclusions: A score of 82 indicates high quality. Recording desired place of death, preventing critical incidents, costs, and coordination require attention. Only those with patient contact are best suited to assess the quality of outpatient palliative care.

1. Introduction

For several years, there has been a clear trend in the global demographic development towards an overaged society (McNicoll, 2002). This observation is particularly evident in developed countries such as Switzerland. Consequently, a rise in the population of older individuals with multimorbidity nearing the end of their lives is anticipated (Bundesamt für Statistik, 2020). This presents significant challenges, particularly in outpatient care settings, where greater coordination and tailored solutions are frequently necessary (Stiel et al., 2020). The importance of general and specialized palliative care in the outpatient setting is undisputed (Müller-Busch, 2011). In particular, the benefits for the quality of life and the treatment of symptoms at the end of life have been emphasized (Kavalieratos et al., 2016; Zimmermann et al., 2008).

At the end of life, the need for healthcare services is high and often associated with increased admission to inpatient facilities (Bähler et al., 2016). Unnecessary hospitalizations for patients at the end of their lives can be reduced by well-functioning outpatient palliative care concepts (Hurni et al., 2024; Taylor et al., 2020), with decreased healthcare costs (Gonzalez-Jaramillo et al., 2021; McCarroll et al., 2022). Good palliative care may facilitate the possibility of dying at home (Costa et al., 2016; Gomes et al., 2013a; Jordhøy et al., 2000). Many palliative care patients express this wish (Gomes et al., 2013b), yet it does not reflect the current reality. Data from Switzerland show that only approximately 20% of people die at home (Zehnder, 2019). Fulfilling the patient's wish to die at home not only generally corresponds to a criterion for a good quality of death (Downey et al., 2010; Patrick et al., 2001), but also forms one of several quality criteria in palliative care (de Boer et al., 2017; Steinhäuser et al., 2000).

A recently published study by Finkelstein et al. (2022) conducted a global survey on the quality of death, including Switzerland and 80 other countries. In Switzerland, a separate quality label (qualitépalliative (qualitepalliative, 2025a)) was introduced following the National Strategy for Palliative Care (Bundesamt für Gesundheit BAG, 2014). This independent organization uses defined quality standards to assess palliative care institutions. If the criteria are met, these institutions are awarded the "qualitépalliative" label, which is reviewed on an ongoing basis by means of regular recertifications.

A 2018 study on behalf of the Swiss Federal Office of Public Health (FOPH) assessed the status and implementation of palliative care in all Swiss cantons. Due to Switzerland's federal healthcare system, each canton is responsible for organizing its own healthcare system, including palliative care programmes. The study included a qualitative assessment of the cantonal palliative care situation (Liechti and Künzi, 2019) and focused on data collection in form of feedback from cantonal healthcare authorities and regional palliative care organisations. However, direct service providers such as home care nurses were not included, and no quality assessments among the cantons were conducted.

Therefore, our study aimed to assess the quality of outpatient palliative care on a national level and included the most important pillars of outpatient palliative care, namely the direct service providers and institutions with palliative care mandates.

2. Methods

2.1. Study design

This cross-sectional study used an online survey to evaluate the quality of palliative care in the outpatient setting in Switzerland. We adhered to the CROSS guidelines for methodological recommendations and reporting (*Sharma et al., 2021*).

2.2. Study population

The data collected covered the whole of Switzerland with all 26 cantons.

We defined 3 groups of participants: Participants had to be involved in (i) the day to day work in the palliative care setting, (ii) coordination, or (iii) politics.

- a) The first group involved direct service providers, mostly home care nurses, and institutions with close contact to outpatient palliative care. Due to the different sizes of the cantons, we made sure that we could include at least 2 direct service providers per canton. In the case of larger cantons with several service groups, we included each group with a clear connection to outpatient palliative care.
- b) The second group included representatives of the regional palliative care organisations, some of which are organized on a cross-cantonal basis. These regional palliative care organisations act as contact points for counselling and political mediation. All 14 existing organisations throughout Switzerland belonging to the "palliative.ch" organisation were included (*palliative.ch, 2025*).
- c) The third group comprised of representatives of the cantonal healthcare authorities of all 26 Swiss cantons.

The relevant contact details were researched in the form of an extensive internet search. Additional contact details were also requested as part of the survey. Potential participants nominated by participants in the first mailing phase were included in a second mailing phase.

Individual cantons were grouped into regions to protect the anonymity of the participants. We orientated ourselves on the major-regions of Switzerland defined by the Federal Statistical Office: Région Lémanique and Espace Mittelland (grouped into "Western Switzerland"), Northwestern Switzerland, Central Switzerland and Zurich ("Northern and Central Switzerland"), and Eastern Switzerland and Ticino ("Eastern Switzerland") (*Bundesamt für Raumentwicklung ARE, 2025; Bundesamt für Statistik, 2005*).

2.3. Questionnaire development and data collection

The data was collected with an online questionnaire created by "Qualtrics" ("*Qualtrics XM,*" 2025). The questionnaire was divided into five sections.

- i. Ten demographic questions, including information on cantonal affiliation, type of territory (urban, rural or intermediate region), associated category (direct service provider, cantonal healthcare authority, regional palliative care organisation), associated professional group, gender, age, any completed education in palliative care, work experience, and direct patient contact as part of daily work.

- ii. Nine questions on the status of outpatient palliative care in the respective canton, specifically on the existence of outpatient service providers with an explicit palliative care mandate within the respective canton or additional services as part of a basic care mandate, questions about the existence of 24-h coverage in terms of specialist counselling and contact by phone. The structure of the questions consisted largely of multiple-choice answers. Corresponding answer options were "yes", "no" or "don't know". Where required by the question construction, free-text answers were possible.
- iii. Twenty questions assessing the general quality of palliative care, based on a study by *Finkelstein et al. (2022)*, which defined and validated 13 quality indicator questions. These questions were translated into the respective survey language and integrated unchanged into the questionnaire. Using 5-point Likert items, a quality score could be calculated (max. 100 points), as explained elsewhere (*Finkelstein et al., 2022*). In addition, the option of selecting the answers "Don't know" or "Not applicable" was offered. The questions within this block were randomized. The seven supplementary questions used by *Finkelstein et al. (2022)* were also adapted for Switzerland.
- iv. Eight questions addressed further quality indicators derived from the "qualitépalliative" (*qualitepalliative, 2025b*) audit criteria, to assess mobile palliative care teams, structures and actions. In favor of the practicability of the questionnaire, this section was limited to the most relevant questions.
- v. Three final questions focused on clarifying the remaining areas of action around outpatient palliative care coverage.

Responding to multiple choice questions was mandatory, i.e. leaving questions unanswered was not possible. The participants were asked to respond to the supply situation in their respective area of responsibility when answering the questionnaire. The detailed questionnaire can be found in the online supplementary material.

The questionnaire was discussed within and revised by the entire research team. In addition, the contents of the questions were checked for comprehensibility together with an external medical specialist who has training in palliative care.

As part of the survey pilot with five participants from the field of palliative care, the time required to complete the questionnaire was measured and attention was paid to clarity and unambiguity of questions. Any ambiguities were discussed with the pilot participants and corrected in the final questionnaire. The participants in the pilot were excluded from the final study.

Given Switzerland's multilingual landscape, all relevant documents sent to study participants were translated into French and Italian. To check that the content of the translation was correct, the generated documents were translated back into German by a second person.

Finally, the content of the respective versions was checked again.

2.4. Survey administration

The online survey was conducted 9/2023–12/2023. The participants were contacted by email with a link to the online questionnaire. In the accompanying message, we emphasized to recipients that the survey should be internally disseminated to the individuals most qualified in palliative care. We also appealed for honesty when

completing the questions. In the first mailing phase, all 26 health authorities, all 14 palliative care organisations and a total of 71 direct service providers were contacted. In case of no response, a new invitation to participate was sent to the respective participants after 4 weeks. After a further 4 weeks without a response, the participants were contacted personally again.

2.5. Ethical considerations

Ethical approval for this study was waived by the local ethics committee (Req-2023-00966). The answers of the participants were evaluated anonymously.

2.6. Data analysis

One author had access to all incoming responses. All data contents were translated into English. The statistical analysis was carried out using R, version 4.3.1 (R Foundation for Statistical Computing, Vienna, Austria).

Categorical variables are presented as counts and percentages, continuous variables with non-normal distributions as medians and interquartile ranges (IQR). Fisher exact tests were used to compare categorical variables between groups, Kruskal-Wallis tests to compare continuous variables.

In order to evaluate the existence of a palliative care service in a specific canton, all responses from all participants in the respective canton were aggregated and evaluated. If at least 80% of the participants answered the question in the same way ("Yes" or "No"), their response counted. If there was no majority of a clear answer ($\geq 80\%$) within a canton, the response was considered as discordant.

Summarizing tables were created for the questions that listed the answer categories "Yes", "No" and "Don't know". A mean, median and mode were calculated for the corresponding questions. The mean was calculated by assigning a numerical value to the individual answer categories ("Yes" = 1, "Don't know" = 0, "No" = -1). The median denotes the response category that lies exactly in the middle of the data distribution. The mode corresponds to the response category most frequently mentioned.

Independent associations with a quality score (*Finkelstein et al., 2022*) above the median were investigated by multivariable logistic regression models, providing odds ratios (OR) and 95% confidence intervals (95%CI). All models adjusted for gender, duration of employment (without age to avoid multicollinearity), geographic region, population density, and whether the participant had patient contact.

The first model analysed whether the "subjective quality assessment" (question Q36) was associated with higher quality scores. Eight further models investigated whether the "qualité palliative" audit criteria associated with scores above the median. Since the latter required to run one model for each criterion, we controlled for multiple testing by applying the Bonferroni method, additionally presenting a p-value for each exposure variable (i.e. criterion): In these models, if a p-value was below $0.05/8 = 0.00625$ the association was considered as statistically significant, a p-value between 0.05 and 0.00625 indicated a trend.

Since the quality score (*Finkelstein et al., 2022*) can only be calculated for participants who answered all 13 questions (Q20-Q32) with one of the five Likert item responses (i.e. "Strongly disagree" = 1, "Somewhat disagree" = 2, "Neither agree nor disagree" = 3, "Somewhat agree" = 4, "Strongly agree" = 5), we used multiple imputation for all participants who entered such responses for 9 to 12 questions (i.e. $>69\%$ answered). If they answered fewer questions, their records were not considered in the regression analyses.

3. Results

3.1. Participant characteristics

A total of 141 participants completed the online survey, we received at least 4 responses per canton.

An overview of the participating population is shown in Table 1. The median age of the entire population was 51 years, and 80% of respondents were female. In total, 52% of the participants (n = 73) were nurses, 13% worked in the medical sector (n = 19), and 35% of the participants (n = 49) belonged to a non-medical or unspecified professional group. The proportion of participants with patient contact was 69% (n = 97), decreasing from palliative care service providers to cantonal authorities. Approximately two thirds of palliative care service providers were home care nurses.

3.2. Palliative care provision structures

Table 2 illustrates the cantonal palliative care provision structures as perceived by participants. Participants agreed that specific outpatient palliative care providers are present in almost all cantons (n = 24).

Table 1: Characteristics of participants.

	Palliativ care service provider	Regional palliative care section	Cantonal authority	p-value
n	96	15	30	
Gender = Male (%)	22 (22.9)	3 (20.0)	3 (10.0)	0.302
Age (median [IQR])	51 [43.75, 57]	54 [48.5, 58.5]	51 [41, 58.5]	0.44
Region (%)				0.982
Eastern Switzerland	23 (24.0)	4 (26.7)	8 (26.7)	
Northern and Central Switzerland	36 (37.5)	5 (33.3)	12 (40.0)	
Western Switzerland	37 (38.5)	6 (40.0)	10 (33.3)	
Population Density (%)				0.028
Intermediate (both or neither)	40 (41.7)	13 (86.7)	16 (53.3)	
Rural	34 (35.4)	1 (6.7)	9 (30.0)	
Urban	22 (22.9)	1 (6.7)	5 (16.7)	
Occupation category (%)				<0.001
Authorities representative	0 (0.0)	0 (0.0)	21 (70.0)	
Manager	16 (16.7)	7 (46.7)	0 (0.0)	
Medical staff	16 (16.7)	2 (13.3)	1 (3.3)	
Nursing staff	61 (63.5)	4 (26.7)	8 (26.7)	
Other	3 (3.1)	2 (13.3)	0 (0.0)	
Duration of employment (median [IQR])	6.5 [3, 12]	7 [1.75, 9]	6 [2.25, 16.5]	0.444
Patient contact = Yes (%)	84 (87.5)	7 (46.7)	6 (20.0)	<0.001
Education in palliative care = Yes (%)	76 (79.2)	9 (60.0)	9 (30.0)	<0.001

Table 2: Cantonal palliative care provision structures (n=26 cantons).

Question/availability in your canton	Response	N cantons
Service providers who offer outpatient palliative care	Yes	24
	No	0
	Discordant	2
Specialized service providers who exclusively work in the field of home-based palliative care	Yes	12
	No	0
	Discordant	14
"Spitex" (home care service) has a cantonal mandate for palliative care	Yes	8
	No	1
	Discordant	17
Professionals specialized in palliative care employed by "Spitex" (home care service)	Yes	20
	No	0
	Discordant	6
Mobile palliative care service or outpatient palliative care consultation service to support palliative care at home	Yes	20
	No	0
	Discordant	6
Palliative care outpatient clinic	Yes	3
	No	5
	Discordant	18
24-hour availability of a specialized palliative care professionals for palliative patients	Yes	14
	No	1
	Discordant	11

However, discordant responses were recorded for the questions whether a canton has a palliative care outpatient clinic and whether "Spitex" (home care service) has a cantonal mandate for palliative care (discordant responses for 18 and 17 cantons, respectively).

3.3. Quality score of palliative care provision

Fig. 1 shows an overview of the 13 quality indicator questions. A detailed table presenting all questions and all responses is included in the online supplement.

A total of 100 participants (70.9%) responded to all 13 questions so that the quality score could be calculated, resulting in a median score of 82.2 points. Of participants seeing patients, 84.5% (82/97) answered all 13 questions, whereas 40.9% (18/44) of those without patient contact did ($p < 0.001$). Four participants answered none of the 13 questions, all stating that they did not have patient contact.

Palliative care service providers rated the quality higher than cantonal authorities and palliative care sections (median scores of 83.8, 77.5 and 75.7, respectively).

The "subjective quality assessment" (Q36) is illustrated in Fig. 2.

To justify the subjective assessment (Fig. 2), participants were asked to mention positive and negative points in free-text responses. A summarized table can be found in the online supplement (supplementary table ST2 and ST3). The most frequently mentioned positive points were the availability of outpatient palliative care ($n = 52$) and the existence of a cantonal strategy or concept ($n = 36$). As negative points, the lack of certain services ($n = 34$), and the financial situation ($n = 32$) in particular, were

viewed critically. Difficulties in the coordination of services were also mentioned (n = 27).

The answers to the questions on the "qualité palliative" label (*qualitepalliative, 2025b*) are summarized in Table 3.

3.4. Regression analyses

While 100 participants provided a quality score, multiple imputation was required for further 27 (19.1%) who answered at least 9 of the 13 quality score questions (14, 7, 2, and 4 participants answered 12, 11, 10, and 9 questions, respectively). Thereby, 90.1% of all participants could be included in the regression analyses.

The first regression model (Supplementary Table ST5) showed that a participant's "subjective quality assessment" in comparison with other cantons (Q36) was independently, statistically significantly associated with a quality score above the median (OR 1.62, 95%CI 1.15, 2.32).

The regression models analysing the "qualité palliative" (*qualitepalliative, 2025b*) criteria revealed that the availability and use of three measures was independently, statistically significantly associated with quality scores above the median (Table 4; Supplementary Tables ST6-ST13). The association was strongest for recording the desired place of death, with an OR of nearly 7, followed by measures to prevent critical incidents, and recording critical incidents. With ORs of 5 and 4, strong trends towards higher quality scores were identified for planning ahead of emergencies, and addressing needs of family members, respectively.

Figure 1: Overall rating of the 13 quality indicators.

Figure 2: Rating of the quality of outpatient palliative care in own canton compared to other cantons.

Table 3: Summarized presentation of the answers to the questions on the "qualitépalliative" label (*qualitepalliative, 2025b*).

Question number	Question	Mean	Median	Mode	Yes/No-Responded	Yes/No-Responded %	Response	N	%
40	Do service providers with patient contact inquire about and record the desired place of death (home, nursing home, hospice, hospital, etc.) of the patients?	0.7	Yes (1)	Yes (1)	108	76.6	Yes (1)	100	70.9
							No (-1)	8	5.7
							Don't know (0)	33	23.4
41	Do service providers take measures during the dying process (as far as possible) to facilitate the desired place of death?	0.8	Yes (1)	Yes (1)	117	83.0	Yes (1)	117	83.0
							No (-1)	0	0.0
							Don't know (0)	24	17.0
42	Is an advance directive recorded, and if not available, is support offered for its documentation?	0.6	Yes (1)	Yes (1)	113	80.1	Yes (1)	102	72.3
							No (-1)	11	7.8
							Don't know (0)	28	19.9
43	Is an emergency plan created, as well as prescriptions for emergency medications?	0.8	Yes (1)	Yes (1)	117	83.0	Yes (1)	112	79.4
							No (-1)	5	3.5
							Don't know (0)	24	17.0
44	Are the needs of family members identified and are they actively offered support?	0.8	Yes (1)	Yes (1)	115	81.6	Yes (1)	111	78.7
							No (-1)	4	2.8
							Don't know (0)	26	18.4
45	Do service providers have tools or processes in place to measure patient and family satisfaction?	0.1	Don't know (0)	Don't know (0)	86	61.0	Yes (1)	52	26.9
							No (-1)	34	24.1
							Don't know (0)	55	39.0
46	Are critical incidents systematically recorded by service providers?	0.3	Don't know (0)	Yes (1)	83	58.9	Yes (1)	61	43.3
							No (-1)	22	15.6
							Don't know (0)	58	41.1
47	Are appropriate measures decided upon and implemented regarding critical incidents?	0.4	Don't know (0)	Don't know (0)	72	51.1	Yes (1)	63	44.7
							No (-1)	9	6.4
							Don't know (0)	69	48.9

3.5. Free-text recommendations on how to improve outpatient palliative care

Most participants recommended to expand the service of palliative care (supplementary table ST4), e.g. by establishing 24-h coverage (n = 31) and increasing the number of palliative care specialists (n = 27). Further, efforts should be made for the education of nursing staff (n = 34) and physicians (n = 28). Some participants suggested the implementation of standardised quality measures (n = 13). The improvement of care coordination was also mentioned: There is a perceived need to improve the exchange of information between inpatient and outpatient settings (n = 23), as well as cooperation with general practitioners (n = 16). Many participants mentioned the need for increased funding of specialized palliative care services (n = 56). Finally, some participants suggested improving awareness of palliative care issues among the general public (n = 15), general practitioners (n = 12) and health insurance companies or authorities (n = 9).

Table 4: Eight multivariable logistic regression models investigated potential associations between "qualitépalliative" criteria (*qualitepalliative*, 2025b) and quality scores above the median. Due to the Bonferroni correction for multiple testing, independent associations are considered as statistically significant if the p-value is below 0.00625 (bold p-values).

Exposure: "qualitépalliative" criterion	OR	(95% CI)	p-value
Q40: Do service providers with patient contact inquire about and record the desired place of death (home, nursing home, hospice, hospital, etc.) of the patients?	6.73	(2.72,21.32)	0.0002
Q41: Do service providers take measures during the dying process (as far as possible) to facilitate the desired place of death?	3.52	(0.97,16.79)	0.07
Q42: Is an advance directive recorded, and if not available, is support offered for its documentation?	1.48	(0.78,2.88)	0.2
Q43: Is an emergency plan created, as well as prescriptions for emergency medications?	5.13	(1.71,23.16)	0.01
Q44: Are the needs of family members identified and are they actively offered support?	4.34	(1.48,19.31)	0.02
Q45: Do service providers have tools or processes in place to measure patient and family satisfaction?	1.43	(0.91,2.28)	0.1
Q46: Are critical incidents systematically recorded by service providers?	2.11	(1.26,3.66)	0.005
Q47: Are appropriate measures decided upon and implemented regarding critical incidents?	5.78	(2.81,12.99)	0.000006

OR: odds ratio

95% CI: 95% confidence interval

All models adjusted for gender, duration of employment, region, population density, and whether the participant had patient contact.

All included variables were categorical except for the exposure variables Q40-Q47, which were included as numerical variables using the values

"No" = -1,

"Don't know" = 0,

"Yes" = 1

4. Discussion

4.1. Summary of main findings

This study explored the provision and quality of outpatient palliative care in Switzerland in the perception of stakeholders represented by direct palliative care service providers, members of regional palliative care organisations, and cantonal authority members.

We found that the overall quality of outpatient palliative care as assessed by the respondents was "high", with a median score of 82.2 points. However, palliative care service providers rated the quality higher than palliative care sections (median scores of 83.8, 75.7, respectively). Still, regression modelling a higher quality score outcome in relation to higher comparative quality as perceived by participants was independently positively associated.

Regarding the quality indicators surveyed, the question about "treated kindly" showed the highest level of agreement (98%), followed by "managed pain and discomfort" (98%) and "Quality of life extending treatments" (95%). This shows that overall the relevant palliative care activities, which are aimed precisely at these points, are well fulfilled.

In terms of positive aspects, the participants appreciate the range of outpatient palliative care services (n = 52) and the existence of a cantonal palliative care concept or law (n = 36). The study participants were therefore generally satisfied with the current structure of services and considered a political concept or law to be very important.

On the negative side, the questions on the quality indicators "Cost were not a barrier" (44%), "Care was well-coordinated" (19%) and "Preferred place of death" (14%) had the highest proportion of disagreement. This was also reported multiple times in the free-text comments, especially in the areas of finances (n = 32) and collaboration/coordination (n = 27). Participants have identified these thematic areas as having the greatest need for improvement. In the area of coordination and collaboration (n = 61), participants still rated the situation as inadequate. The quality of outpatient palliative care could be further improved through standardized tools and appropriate communication channels. A significant area in need of improvements in outpatient palliative care, as mentioned by 56 participants, is the financial situation, either through better remuneration for palliative care services or financial support to promote initiatives. Other recommendations made by the study participants included the expansion of outpatient palliative care to 24-h coverage and the need for more professionally trained staff.

The results of the study further showed that the systematic use of three measures suggested by "qualitépalliative" (*qualitepalliative*, 2025a), i.e. the recording of the desired place of death, the recording and the prevention of critical incidents, are associated with higher quality in outpatient palliative care. These results stayed valid even after the application of the conservative Bonferroni method for multiple testing. Strong trends towards higher quality scores were also found for planning ahead of emergencies and addressing the needs of family members.

4.2. Comparison with existing literature

The results of the study regarding the quality score for Switzerland can be compared with findings from the reference study by *Finkelstein et al. (2022)*. Their study globally surveyed entire nations and Switzerland was one of the represented countries: The score for Switzerland was 87.6 points. In comparison to the Finkelstein study

(*Finkelstein et al., 2022*), where only two palliative care experts in Switzerland were surveyed, 100 participants representing all cantons provided a score in our study, resulting in a slightly lower rating.

The Federal Office of Public Health investigates the range of palliative care services and quality in a 5-yearly survey, most recently in November 2023 (*Ecoplan, 2023*). In common with our study, all cantonal healthcare authorities and all regional palliative care organisations were surveyed. However, in contrast to our study, the other survey was setting-independent thus not making a distinction between the different palliative care settings, and more importantly, direct service providers were not included in their survey. Furthermore, in an earlier study by the Swiss government (*Liechti and Künzi, 2019*), only the cantonal healthcare authorities and regional palliative care organisations were included for methodological reasons.

While our study focuses exclusively on the outpatient setting, the studies of the Federal Office of Public Health surveyed the entire spectrum of palliative care, including inpatient and long-term care facilities. In addition, the focus of the Federal Office of Public Health's study was on service structures. An assessment of the existing quality was only briefly surveyed, without the use of clearly defined quality indicators. However, in the survey conducted by the Federal Office of Public Health in 2023 (*Ecoplan, 2023*), the majority of cantonal healthcare authorities and regional palliative care organisations rated the quality of specialized palliative care in both the hospital and outpatient sectors as high, which was evaluated in a three-likert-item question (good – satisfactory – bad). The regional palliative care organisations rated the quality of general palliative care significantly more critical than the cantonal healthcare authorities. In the previous survey in 2018 (*Liechti and Künzi, 2019*), the regional palliative care organisations also rated the quality for specialized palliative care higher compared to general palliative care.

The 2023 study (*Ecoplan, 2023*) also evaluated the situation regarding coordination among service providers. This was rated as good or satisfactory by 88% of the cantons and by 57% of the regional palliative care organisations. The survey of cantons revealed that the focus of cantonal funding measures also lies in the area of developing and expanding coordination of services. Regarding reimbursement, 12 cantons have their own performance agreements with service providers, while 11 cantons provide (partial) financing. However, in line with our findings, a recent study on a novel specialized mobile palliative care service in rural Lucerne also identified coordination as an important challenge (*Bucher et al., 2024*).

Besides these surveys commissioned by the Swiss government, after extensive further literature research also considering all recent publications citing the work by *Finkelstein et al. (2022)*, it appears that our study is the first comprehensive assessment of the quality of outpatient palliative care as perceived by providers and representatives on a national scale.

4.3. Limitations and strengths

The results of our study should be interpreted in the light of several limitations. First, the questions on the existing range of outpatient palliative care services showed some discrepant results within a canton. As a result, we are not able to provide objective feedback in every case. We think that the main problem could be found in partial ambiguity or incomprehensibility of some questions, which was not detected during pilot testing of the survey. However, present an objective approach on how to follow-up and present potential changes in future studies that would be comparable to our baseline. Second, the finding that direct service providers rated the quality of palliative

care slightly higher could be interpreted as possible social desirability bias: The argument that direct service providers do not want to present their activities as poor in terms of quality is understandable. However, the quality indicator questions focus primarily on structural problems and not on professional expertise, thereby attenuating this potential issue. And finally, the fact that only palliative care service stakeholders were included in the survey could also be interpreted as a weakness of the study, especially since an assessment of quality by patients is just as important. However, the healthcare system and the corresponding structures and services are first and foremost designed to ensure the satisfaction of patients and relatives. In addition, the assessment of the views of patients and relatives was beyond the scope of this study. As strength, we were able to reach a high coverage of Swiss cantons and of representatives/providers per canton, translating into a sound representativity of findings. In our study, the quality indicator questions have been fully answered by the majority of study participants. The study clearly separated participants of an official setting (cantonal healthcare authority or regional palliative care organisation) from participants of the direct service provider setting with patient contact. To our knowledge, our study is the first to include outpatient service providers with direct patient contact in the assessment of the quality of outpatient palliative care, and it appears that our study is the first comprehensive assessment of the quality of outpatient palliative care on a national scale.

4.4. Implications and future research opportunities

Our results demonstrate that systematically using certain quality standards is associated with a higher palliative care quality rating. Therefore, these quality standards need to be known and implemented by stakeholders involved in outpatient palliative care. According to our collected data, the greatest potential for improvement is found in the areas of finance and coordination. In addition to a sufficiently supported financial basis, service providers would benefit most from a wellfunctioning interdisciplinary collaboration. From our point of view, we see the most important political measures here to promote quality in outpatient palliative care.

Our study's methodological approach has the potential to evaluate the development of palliative care quality, for example by repeatedly carrying out a survey with the questionnaire we used. The methodology of the study would be well suited to assess other palliative care settings. Inpatient services, as well as long-term care facilities and hospices would be a suitable target audience for conducting a quality assessment, especially including palliative care service providers again. In addition to other care systems, it would be interesting to evaluate more specific areas of palliative care (e.g. paediatric palliative care, psychiatric palliative care, people with disabilities) with regard to existing services and quality.

And finally, beyond the perception of professionals in our study, the perception of patients in palliative conditions and their relatives would be of utmost importance, as they are the ultimate recipients of palliative care, and the corresponding quality matters to them the most.

5. Conclusion

The majority of stakeholders who participated in the study expressed agreement, rating utilized quality indicators as either “somewhat agree” or “strongly agree”. The greatest discrepancy was found in the area of costs and the coordination of services. In addition to the expansion of specialized services, the greatest potential for improvement was also described here to improve the quality of outpatient palliative care in order to ensure best care for palliative patients and their families.

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